

Unveiling Cross Cultural Relationship in Anuradha D. Rajurkar's '*American Betiya*'

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Abstract

This research has been made to probe and investigate cross cultural relationship by applying Lisa Lowe's theory of Heterogeneity, Hybridity, Multiplicity: Marking Asian American Differences. The project mainly deals with Indian and American families who are interacting with each other in America. Researchers have discussed, all the main characters, in order to study their struggle for identity. Anuradha D. Rajurkar's *American Betiya* is taken as the primary text to probe how Indian culture is suppressed in the dominant American society due to cross-cultural differences. Research will also clarify this fact that people from Asian countries dream about America as an ideal land where their every wish would be fulfilled, but after arriving there, they find themselves on the suffering end due to cultural differences. To avoid psychological suffering, the only way to be successful in America is by adopting oneself and carrying on with American norms and traditions without any resistance. One finding of this research is that in the process of unveiling cross-cultural relationship, the researchers are able to state that these cross-cultural relations cannot be successful until or unless individuals are thriving with their prejudicial intolerance. There are problems with the followers of both cultures that are creating impediments in the way of leading healthy cross-cultural relationships. Thus, a happy cross-cultural relationship still remains a myth, a paradigm still to be achieved.

Keywords: Cross cultural, Unveiling, Heterogeneity, Hybridity, Multiplicity

1. Introduction

The term unveiling has deep meaning, it is not something that should be considered to convey the message that individuals are refuting something or unveiling is something the stage of disagreement rather unveiling lies with the idea to remove the disguise and the truth among the fraudulent approaches of the societies. Unveiling is the method to break into the fabricated screen and to unlock the reality that is hidden from the normal view of the eye. Unveiling is done to uncover the sanctimony and animosity prevailing in the society. By unveiling researcher can analyze the ideas, revolutionary movements, see through people's motives behind it and the principle which are governing them. Here in the research the sole purpose will be to deal with the unveiling of cross culturalism.

In this research, researcher is unveiling cross cultural relationship. If one can observe their relationship there is huge diversity among the case of association. It is really a complex thing in human beings, sometime the far of relationships produce great and ideal relationships and sometimes the closest fail to work. Cross cultural is the relation between two cultures accepting their difference and similarities with open heart for the survival of relationship. When reader first hear the word cross cultural relationship the first thing that comes in his mind is the idea of miscommunications and misunderstandings, cross cultural is mainly considered an inability to survive and thrive in the foreign culture. It has nothing to do with the mental state or the psychological state. The reader has to understand that it is something imbedded in the cultural differences. Cross cultural relationship is in the fashion because as the world is becoming global village and after the postcolonial, the great differences emerged and due to more and more connectivity, the relationships are coming in surface that are cross culture in nature.

This research work is an attempt to unveil cross cultural relationship under the light of Lisa Lowe theory Heterogeneity, Hybridity, Multiplicity: Marking Asian American Difference. The subject novel that has been chosen by researcher is *American Betiya* written by Anuradha D. Rajurkar. This novel is about how one Indian family is settled in America. Their parents are considered to be more Indian in the Native American society, struggling to raise generation that has love hate relationship with the American society. Anuradha D. Rajurkar has produced a wonderful piece of art that brush up over thinking and ideals about the amalgamation of Asian and American society. Rajurkar tried to express dilemma about Indian culture and its possibilities to be retained as refined, pure in dominant American society.

1.1. Background of the Study

Cross cultural is a cyber society in progress. There are some factors for cross cultural relationship's nourishment; language, preparation, and awareness are the most important tools to express positive receptor for active cross cultural relationship. Writer of the novel *American Betiya* explored the love affair of two artists who are on the verge of their passionate interracial affair. The family, who is Indian by birth, settled in America and protagonist Indian girl who

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have her American boyfriend. The girl is perfect specimen of Indian family that is why she is addressed as —Betiya in the novel but as she embarks on the journey of cross-cultural relationship, she starts to revolt.

First time this term was used in the 1831 by Thomas Dick in his work. In his piece of writing he explained the mysterious plan of God and he wanted to discuss that symbols of the God are spread throughout the universe and the inquisitive people like Thomas Dick who are curious about the existence and divine scheme of God try to unveil the divine pattern.

The way Thomas Dick was unveiling nature of universe similarly the researcher will try to unveil cross cultural relationship to reveal true nature of these relationships. James Chook used this term in 1836 in his voyage chapter in the context that when they were unveiled, they started to pretend in the mysterious way. Then after that term is used in the religious books and in the religious context. This term unveiling was used for the woman who is sacred by being Muslim in nature and they will never unveil themselves in front of the strangers. So, every reader can see that this term unveiling has been used in so many colorful various contexts.

As cross culture relationship is current phenomenon, people who are adopting it, they must understand the broader spectrum of interpretation, what they are hearing and what they have to comprehend and how they have to respond. Our youth must try to learn these behavioral techniques from the educational institute to cope with the fashion of cross cultural. Sometime the culture of one city is different from the culture of the other city so this term can be applied for that as well but mostly it is taken as cultural exchange between the two people and families of the different countries pertaining to different cultural backgrounds. Now the people want to learn the new things and the personally want to transcend the cultural boundaries and want to experience the new culture so this knowledge is in the fashion as well as the current need of hour. It is the universal proceedings and great approach to understand the cross-cultural relationship. Peter Murdoch, who was an anthropologist, founded this concept of the cross-cultural relationship.

This study came under the considerable importance because now due to modern advancement in the technology there is huge amount of movements between the different culture and vast amount of knowledge is required for a controlled response in the foreign culture. Great cognitive control is being taught in the modern books that if one moves from one culture to another what they have to imbibe, when they have to strike with rationality and when they have retained and stay persistent to their own native culture. Now a day this branch is currently dealing with the human relationship studies in the branch of anthropology. This cross-cultural research studies are so important in the modern era because everyone have different ratio of opinions about the cross-cultural relationship, when the things are discussed on the online platform and they are quite the opposite of the one who are experiencing it in the relationship and at the work places practically.

Lisa Lowe in her theory expressed concerns about Asian American differences and marks Asian American differences. While on the other hand the world wants to see the cultural syncretism which is difficult, if not impossible according to Lisa Lowe. The whole theory revolves around marking Asian American difference, their individual battle to retain norm customs, traditions and cultures. One will observe heterogeneity, which will occur throughout the relations emerging, sometimes it will be transformed into the hybridity and after the deep amalgamation and mixing of cultures, and people can observe the multiplicity. When an Asian travel to America they want to retain their cultural norm till their death fighting and struggling with American culture so detainment continues throughout the novel.

The writer of novel *American Betiya* explored the love affair of two artists who are on the verge of their passionate interracial affair. The family, who is Indian by birth, settled in America and protagonist Indian girl who have her American boyfriend. The girl is perfect specimen of Indian family that is why she is addressed as —Betiya in the novel but as she embarks on the journey of cross-cultural relationship, she starts to revolt. The girl who never lied with her parents starts lying; the girl who never met someone with drug addictions starts an affair with the one American who is addicted to drugs. Girl who hated tattoos on body falls in love with tattooed figure of American boyfriend. Fitting and adjusting with each other and surviving, while appreciating other partner culture is considered as betrayal of both towards their culture. This novel explores the boundaries and hardships of cross-cultural relationships. What are the hurdles and what are the limitations of the culture that limit the relationships and there are factors that test them according to different parameters prevailing in the European society for Indian family.

1.2. Research Questions

The researcher is making this research to answer following pertinent questions.

- How does conservative dominance of Asian parents make Rani Kelkar, the protagonist, suffer in American society?
- Why cultural clash is inevitable for Indian family while living in America by keeping in view of Anuradha's *American Betiya*?

1.3. Research Objectives

This study aims to:

- Evaluate how conservative dominance of Asian parents make Rani Kelkar, the protagonist, suffer in American society
- Analyze why cultural clash is inevitable for Indian family while living in America by keeping in view of Anuradha's *American Betiya*

1.4. Scope of the Study

The study is to investigate heterogeneity and to observe how one culture of colonized is diverse from the culture of colonizers and what will happen when an Asian family will be settled in the American society and to explore dilemma of cross-cultural relationship and people coming after us to enlighten them that how people and colonial rule has impacted our contemporary surroundings. Changes on the map of world are drastic if one brings account of cultural values. The study not only focuses on the individual relationship, one relationship should not be taken as microcosmic study it is the deep macrocosmic study which expands beyond the cultural boundaries.

1.5. Statement of the Problem

This investigation is considered as an attempt to scrutinize and consider the identity as fluid and it should not be considered as something rigid but clash of cultural values among conservatism and secularism can be traced throughout research product. The researcher through this works want to highlight the familial issues of cross-cultural relations and issues that are relating to extra love life relations among the Asian and American families. The researcher wants to emphasize and feature the role of conservative dominance of Indian parents and how this is affecting cross cultural relationship.

1.6. Limitation of the Study

This study is an intense effort to probe identity and the politics and fight for survival in the European society in the context of Asian American relationship. These inequitable arguments are comprehensibly defended and raised to the relative contribution to the disciplines such as sociology, cultural study and political science study. The study addresses to unveiling cross cultural relationship and contributes to the question raised through the writing of Anuradha D. Rajurkar who represents Asian family The limitation that was faced is that the field of literature is full of evidence for discussing heterogeneity, hybridity and multiplicity but here in this research, researcher is limited just to one novel and all the references collected are from considering predominantly from one novel that is of Anuradha D. Rajurkar's *American Betiya*.

2. Literature Review

The main purpose of writing literature review is to audit and position this research product according to other literature produced in this context. There have been many literary texts produced in this context and convey the same message that has been conveyed in *American Betiya* written by Anuradha D. Rajurkar. Many writers, researchers, critics have tried to approach the same subject matter and has always brought up new and different interpretations according to their thinking. Although in this research, researcher has critically evaluated Anuradha D. Rajurkar work. Writer has expressed the idea of cross-cultural relationship in which there are twists and turns, all the main characters are on the suffering position due to their exposure in the new cultural environment. Some elderly characters in novel are strongly attached to their native culture while some (young generation) is ready to change and adopt according to changing circumstances in the global world.

Researcher will discuss the perspective according to the works in which writers has discussed Asian American relationship. Researchers' work is unique because so far all the works that has been produced in the literature are according to the Japanese relationship with Americans or the Chinese relationship with the Americans.

Janice Mirikitani (1978) and her poem are discussed in this context of cross-cultural relationship, the poem is written in very easy language and any indulgent reader can interpret it. The poem gives us insight into three generations. This poem is written according to narrative of mother. This mother is expressing her relationship and experience in dealing with her ancestors and same mother is also narrating her life experience while bringing up her daughter in his world. In this way researcher is able to observe experiences and reaction to problems of all these three different generations. The mother who is narrator of poem is connecting daughter and grandmother representing all three generation by her voice. Narrator has resentment for her mother's time period and her limitations that were imposed on it. All cultures that were observed by narrator were designed for women's suffering according to her. In the final portion the daughter is able to stand for her values and to break the tradition. Researcher can clearly analyze that same_ woman curse in the society prevailing on three generation.

Another poem in the same context by Lydia Lowe (1988), there are different division of the Chinese workers on the basis of their generations, and present generation is stronger in difference of language and class. The entire theme is about breaking and revolting against tradition and values prevailing on certain individual. It is about the American capitalist society who has brought on a young woman on to such verge that she has become authoritative to the ladies

of higher age than her. Narrator is enforced in American society to follow American rules because it is her immigration policy and demand of the society that she is leading. She has left her parental house and in order to survive in American society, she is following the norms, customs and traditions of America. Similarly, Gramsci argued that —consent to the rule of the dominant group is achieved by the spread of ideologies—beliefs, assumptions, and values—through social institutions such as schools, churches, courts, and the media, among others (Gramsci, A, 1947). So, this is clear reflection of cross-cultural relations and interactions leading to moral degradation.

Similarly Maxine Hong Kingston's *The Woman Warrior* (1975) and another novel *The Joy Luck Club* (1989) by Amy Tan are also about the generation clash in the different society. It is about mother and daughter relationship and their cultural clash that has persisted in the prevailing society. It is about how American culture dictates the Asian culture. How people following the Chinese culture are subservient to the American society. The researcher and readers can see in the novels written in perspectives of cross-cultural relationships that the cultural value means different to native Chinese and it means different to immigrant Chinese living in the America. Cultural inheritance from Chinese generation to their Chinese generation is different in context if Chinese environment is given. Now the daughter feels guilt when she adopts the American social parameters, she feels guiltier while surviving there. The question of cultural syncretism keeps lurking and it is job of researcher; to reach at some appropriate solution to the question cultural syncretism to such a level that the result should be plausible to the future researchers and lucid in nature of objectives. Well in the novel, *The Woman Warrior* (Kingston, M.H., 1975) suggest that we can change the surrounding of the people but what is inside their hearts we cannot change that and this is a bitter reality. The parental generation who loved their culture from heart will never let go their cultural value but the daughter generation who has been brought in American environment can easily be molded, but time and the battle continue and this is the beauty of retaining their ancestral culture in American society. Asian culture consists of Japanese, Indian, Chinese Philippine, Korean, Vietnamese in the context of Diasporas the Asian in America are resisting to the American society and they are resisting to the change. They are unstable and at constant clash. When researcher use the term that the Asian American as heterogeneous society it just to destroy American cultural dominance based on their values. However, the whole American society is dealing the Asian immigrant on the racial parameters and this can be observed throughout the novels written by Asian writers representing the Asians in the American society. University quotas in the American universities are the example of homogeneous model of amalgamating the minority model.

Hegemony written by Antonio Gramsci (1947) narrates that the hegemony does not deal only with the dominant powerful culture it also deals with the emerging minority culture because it is the battle of two cultures similarly this research revolves around a complete discussion of multiple narratives of both dominant and minority culture reflecting Asian American relationship. Heterogeneity gives rise to the multiplicity and amalgamation of dominant and minority culture with constantly shifting of politics in the America. If the dominant culture resists the minority, they reveal the nature of society instead of concealing it. According to Gramsci, hegemony (—predominance by consent) is a condition in which a fundamental class exercises a political, intellectual, and moral role of leadership within a hegemonic system cemented by a common worldview or —organic ideology. (Gramsci, A, 1947). Fanon (*A Dying Colonialism*, 1959) has written it and observed that in his life the average class assimilation and average class nationalism conforming to the mind set of colonialism masters.

Discourse about assimilation and nationalism comes to the verge of clarification when we will see and observe ethnic reality. Frank Chin (*Aiiee*, 1974) who attacked and some others their fellows on the Maxine Hong Kingston (1975) which were the major publishers of the works on the assimilation of Kingston. The major and primary target is *The Woman Warrior* (1975) researcher has chosen the novel (*The Woman Warrior*) for the criticism while discussing Asian American relationship is a standard. It is the basic yardstick work and the association of language federation is trying to publish proper guide to analyze and interpret *The Woman Warrior* (1975). It is officially declared as a standard work under the banner of Asian America cross cultural relationships. Cervantes' *Don Quixote* (1605) and another novel written by Dante's *Inferno* (1320) are also studied in this context and their guides are being published. These texts are idealized and taken as benchmark for Asian American cross-cultural relationship.

Kingston (1975) has been criticized that they have shown strange, queer, and difference embedded in the Chinese American relationship. The criticism is strong that Asian American men are criticized in such a sense that they cannot fight the white American and the texts that are produced are feminized in nature. There are also claims that Kingston (1975) and Amy Tan (1989) wrote down the Chinese history in such way that they distort the history of Chinese and present them to more patriarchal in nature. So as whole the Asians are taken as more patriarchal and misogynist then compared to the American society. Elaine Kim (1982) in his recent essay —such opposite is very critical and feminist and the nationalists are very much concerned about rising tension between Asian American relationships who states it is a debate about difference and search for identity, and heterogeneity in the interracial relationships. Struggle is between the visible battle between assimilation and nativism.

Louis Chu who has written *Eat of Bowl of Tea* (1961) he allegorized the cultural assimilation and nativism and the conflict is shown between them. It gives us the structure of bachelor society and its conversion to the family society when Ben Loys marriage is arranged by Wah Gay in which a son is shown to obey every one. Again, it is seen that the son was facing no problems in leading active social life before the marriage. Due to active social relations, son destroys himself before his marriage life begins. Chu has written the novel that assimilation and nativism is shown in their relation, in form of sexual affairs. Although it is shown that the son is submitting eagerly to the father's supremacy and admitting his authority, which is not seen in the American culture anywhere openly in text representing American society. All the novels that are written by Chinese writers represent a simple family and the protagonist takes care of the girl after the marriage. That individual is unable to give rise to new generation however in the American novels this thing is cherished that man are having extramarital relationships and man after marriage have nothing to hide and they are also having such healthy relationship with their wives as well. These men of American society don't get shy away from expressing their extra marital relationships. We have to understand the main difference in context of cross-cultural relations that these two cultures are different from their basic values and one should notice that whenever these two cultures will amalgamate then this could be disastrous in nature. In the novel *The Joy Luck Club* (Tan, A, 1989) it raises serious questions on both antagonistic pair of nativism and assimilation. It is the best novel to understand the generational and class conflict among the mother and daughter relationship. It is also best example to delineate the difference between Asian mother and American born daughter.

Peter Wang's movie *A Great Wall* (1986) is constructed in such a way that in many cases there is continuous shift from Beijing scene to the scene placed in the California. The director has done effort to create ideological gap between Asia and America by fluctuating the scenes between the two continents and this all was done with a deliberate effort to express cross cultural relation. How ever there was another message given by giving a title *A Great Wall* (1986) is in such a way that china itself was never pure and it has been constantly invaded by the barbarian and they have been constantly mixing with Chinese culture. So, the director also states that the Asians who are trying to retain their culture pure from the American influence forget that they them self-built this great wall of china to protect them from the other cultures which they could not save and it is considered as myth that the Asian culture is pure. This is the reflection that American has ruined their cultural family setup, it gives rise to cross cultural clash. Now in America there is no family setup and they send their parents to the old houses. While in the Asia, we can see from the scene that children are kept in complete observance and surveillance of the family system and if someone is trying to ruin their family system than they are their American friends who are influenced by American culture.

The relation between the Asian and American is the story of resentment, oppression, resistance, and resilience on the psychological basis from the Asian and Americans families (Yoo.H.C, Gabriel. A. K and Okazaki.S, 2021). Now in the 21st century research scientists have to realize that as in the world, people are becoming global citizen. People must try to eliminate the differences and new values between the similarities of culture should be adopted and everyone must move towards a peaceful future. This is the only way individuals can make an effort to transform the hegemony of America.

3. Theoretical Framework

Well, it is basic issue of cross-cultural relationship and the researcher has applied the theory that fall under the title of "An ethnic literary and cultural study, critical race theory". Theory that the researcher is applying is Lisa Lowe, Heterogeneity, Hybridity, and Multiplicity: Marking Asian American differences. These theories support this research because in this novel of research, whole story revolves around cross cultural relationship. In the whole story reader comes across this deep passionate affair between Asian girl and American boy. It is thoroughly established idea and researcher can produce a standard and potential research work on this, which will guide every reader trying to understand the psychology of cross-cultural relations. This theory of Lisa Lowe is most appropriate theory to be taken as lens to be applied on the novel "*American Betyia*". Key terms are Asian American differences and how the results of Heterogeneity, Hybridity, and Multiplicity are achieved in the cross-cultural relation and its development changes in the families of both Asian and American in response to the cultural aspects that are being antagonistic to each other. Although when the researchers are studying these cross-cultural relationships we mostly consider them to be the postcolonial theory which is most relevant to it. In this research it is the study of Asian American differences which will give rise to the concepts like Heterogeneity, Hybridity, and Multiplicity. The researcher has chosen the theory of Lisa Lowe because it is most relevant theory to be applied on this research novel. It fulfills all the requirements and covers all the aspects of research. This theory is written in the context that holds specific nature and fits deeply into the deep psychological demands of the novel.

4. Research Methodology

The researcher has applied qualitative research methodology and adopted different method in a sense that researcher has read all the texts containing and concerning Asian American relationships which were base ground of this research. The researcher has interpreted the language and analyzed different samples on the basis of ideological framework of cross-cultural relationships. This is a cultural study and to examine a cross cultural relationship under the lens of Lisa Lowe “heterogeneity, hybridity, multiplicity: marking Asian American differences” the researcher has analyzed and concluded that whether this cross-cultural relationship is really toxic in real or it is just perception of people. The study is to look closely and introspect culture of India and its comparison with American culture. This study will give new dimension to cross cultural relationship.

The researcher has analyzed different passages and paragraphs and demystified the myth about hybrid cultural relationships. The researcher has also read poems which are related to this research topic in unveiling cross cultural relationship and their image will be reflected in the conclusion that will be produced at the end of research. Tools and techniques that the researcher has applied are of sharply analyzing the language of novel and theory that were subject matter and scrutinizing the objective on the basis of language used in the text. Samples from the novel were collected and they were keenly probed under the umbrella of cross-cultural relationships. No prejudgment results are produced or tried to be obtained in research rather all results will be based on language and observing characters in the novel and violent image portrayed in the novel reflecting strong evidence for toxic cross-cultural relationship. This method along with objectives and theory that has been applied on the Anuradha D. Rajurkar’ s *American Betiya* is tailor made for each other and that will be seen in the research conclusion.

5. Data Analysis and Discussion

5.1. Dominance of Parents Make Rani Suffer

When individuals are studying cross cultural relationship, readers have to understand the role of Asian parents is pivotal in the upbringing of the children. Asian parents especially south Asians suppress the will of their kids and in process kids lose their own personal choices. This thing is seen in the third world where parents are so much possessive about their children. “Generational conflict”. (Rivkin. J & Ryan. M, 2004, p.1033) These are the basic things but when it comes to relationship they are super possessive about their kids. They have insecurities about the relationships of their children. Similarly Rani said “Parents-whom I love and adoredon’t allow me to date. They’re even uncomfortable with the notion of guy friends.” (p.12). Rani in the above lines clearly shows that she loves her parents and at the same time she talks and reflects her thought about the bindings that her parents are mounting on her, that she cannot fall for any boy and she cannot start a relationship. “So, I have three hyper protective adults to manage” (p. 75) This clearly show that now her interest in Oliver was starting to grow and she wanted to make relationship and progress but on the other hand with the arrival of grandmother things are getting troublesome for the Rani. Rani knew that grandmother who has arrived is complete authoritative figure and she used the term “hyper protective” for her three elder member of Indian family. “Powerless as always” (p.76) Now here one can see the miserable condition of Indian girl battling in the American society. When she uses the term powerless, it clearly reflects that she is helpless. She is in need of someone’s help. This dialogue gives us this impression that woman in the Indian society suffer from painful fate and when these women try to survive in the American society, they are treated as object. The main cause behind this statement is that when woman is in Indian society they are suppressed to such an extent that they losses their own identity.

5.2. Cultural Clash Is Inevitable

There is a scene in novel where time zones are discussed. This scene is multi layered. If people look at its surface level meaning it simply reflects the time zone difference. However, as this novel is in the context of cross-cultural relationship reader have to understand that by expressing the difference writer want to make this point clear by expressing his difference for cross culture relations. “We already called him this evening—which, you know, is morning in India” (p. 201) That America and India are two different world and they are poles apart from each other. Due to so much distance between these two worlds there is great difference of culture and traditions.

There are many events in the novel where something is right and acceptable according to Rani in Indian culture but for Oliver, he analyses it as a flaw and disgusting so that it becomes a joke. There were some religious issues which were holy according to Rani but Oliver enjoyed them as fun story. On the other hand, Oliver was indulged into addiction, drinking, nudity, physical relationships, which were considered to be taboo according to Rani. Likewise, Rani love to wear sari and according to her that sari too is reflection of his tradition of being Indian. “Her left side features a smoky eye glaring like a challenge, body in black, fishnets, and a combat boot. Her opposite side is traditional Indian: a lassy eye lowered, half a blazing red bindi between heavy eyebrows” (p. 231). This is the decisive factor in the novel. Oliver has been studying Rani and her culture since he has been dating her. There was deep

indignation in the mind of Oliver and he wanted to express it. Although he has been hiding his contempt because he wanted that his relationship to thrive with Rani, and she should not be affected by this. At this point in his life he realized after an argumentative clash that it is time to reflect what he has observed so far with his artistic skills. So he designed a huge mural composing female who is divided in to two different and opposing cultural outlooks. All that upon which Rani was differentiated from American culture was completely accepted by Rani and rejected by American boyfriend. Rani knew this and she reflected this in her dialogue: "I TAKE PRIDE IN MY INSECURITIES" (p. 232) Rani used this dialogue when Oliver wanted to meet her family and he wanted that Rani should allow and welcome her into house. Rani was reluctant. Rani knew that her parents will never welcome any American friend. Rani's mother could not even stand a joke about Rani being into relationship, then how will she accept her real American boyfriend. Rani from inside knew that she was not completely ready for her relationship with American boyfriend. She knew she was incomplete regarding this case. It was heart of Rani that brought her to such stage, where she could not stop herself. Here at that point when Oliver drew mural which segmented into two contrasting personalities, same pride factor became cause of her disgust. "can't seem to look away from the mural, like it's a distorted mirror..." (p.233).

Reader can clearly see that Rani, when she was not exposed was taking pride in her insecurities and moment when she received feedback of her insecurities in the form of giant mural, she is shocked. She was standing in front of mural and she was unable to look into any other direction. Her eyes were opened by that mural. She was in suicidal low spirits and it seemed as if she is looking in to mirror that is showing her distorted picture. She could not believe, when her insecurities in which she took pride were brought in front of her in artistic expression by her boyfriend, made her worst nightmare come true. This giant mural of Indian girl that portrayed Rani was so exotic. When Oliver came in front of Rani, she was triggered with emotions of disgust. She perceived as if some stranger has come in front of her. When Oliver touched her she could not recognize his touch. It was Rani's idea that she would recognize hands of Oliver whenever Oliver will touch her, but after this giant mural, Oliver hands were perceived by Rani as some strange hands. From this same hand, Oliver drew two different personalities of Rani. Two personalities inside Rani's consciousness are constantly battling with each other. Oliver brought out that battle and gives it an artistic face and became stranger in the eyes of Rani.

6. Conclusion

This study has focused on dominant Indian parents who are conservative and on the basis of their conservative dominance their kids are suffering. The researcher has clearly discussed all the aspects belonging to nature of Indian parents which are governing them to be dominant in the society. The researcher has also discussed all the reasons behind conservative nature of Indian parents in dominant American society. This behavior of conservative dominance of Indian parents has brought this research to conclusion that due to this behavior their next generation is suffering in American society. Young generation is exposed to American culture and society while living in America. They are getting direct inspiration from society while on returning to their homes; this new breed of Indian is dictated by their parents to stay true to their native Indian culture. In this whole scenario kids are suffering. This Indian generation, being brought up in America is facing problems in cross cultural relation. Anuradha D. Rajurkar has clearly expressed this concern in portrayal of characters that cross cultural relationship is nightmare if Indian parents continue to remain dominating and conservative in American society.

In unveiling cross cultural relationship, the researcher after deep discussion and analysis is able to answer that cultural clash is inevitable for Indian family while living in America. Indian family settled in America has to fight cross cultural war on different fronts. Indian family has to fight their battle for identity just after stepping out of their homes in America. They are treated as constant subject to harassment and abuse by strangers after 9/11. In love life they are treated as exotic Indians. In studies and exhibition of art they are treated as minority culture. In celebration of events they are mocked in derogatory manner. In language and pronunciations they are ridiculed for their articulation. If any Indian continues to stay true to his values then he is victimized for being conservative. Indians are censured for their eating habits.

After above discussion, researcher is able to conclude that there are problems in the followers of both cultures that are creating impediments on the way of leading healthy cross-cultural relationship. Thus, a happy cross cultural relationship still remains a myth, a paradigm still to be achieved.

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